

TECHNICAL INTEROPERABILITY AND CHANGE MANAGEMENT BY INTEGRATING SERVICES OF LOCAL AND REGIONAL INTEREST

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Abstract

Purpose – *In order to establish a public service, public authorities must establish clear organizational relationships.*

Methodology/approach - *Change management is a critical process that ensures the accuracy of data and the continuity and reliability of services provided to other public authorities or institutions, citizens, or businesses, as the provision of a public service is the outcome of the collective effort of parties producing or using components of the service.*

Findings – *In order to maintain the uninterrupted delivery of public services, it is imperative for authorities involved in providing these services to reach a consensus on change management procedures.*

Research limitations/implications – *The subject organization is accountable for the road infrastructure that is controlled by the Sibiu County Council. If the service extends to a regional level and intersects with national level organizations, extending the study findings may necessitate a modified approach to the input data.*

Practical implications – *Technical interoperability connects information systems technically. Interface standards, connectivity services, application integration, data integration, data presentation and sharing, etc. Technical interoperability is not distinctive to public administration institutions, but political, legal, administrative, and partially semantic aspects are. Thus, formalized specifications, such as Directive 98/34/EC standards or ICT industry fora and consortia specifications, should be used to assure technical compatibility.*

Originality/value – *Organizational interoperability include the integration of systems, optimization of business processes, and the sharing of relevant data. Organizational interoperability seeks to fulfill the needs of the user community by providing readily available, easily recognizable, accessible, and user-focused services.*

Key words: *interoperability, change management, public services.*

Introduction

The degree of creative involvement in the development of new solutions, new tools for evaluation, decision, design and strategic execution determines the constraints in today's knowledge-based society rather than the technological level. Knowledge also requires action, and competitive and sustainable action requires forward thinking and a social-entrepreneurial vision on the part of public administration to achieve a sustainable leap in well-being. The

purpose of this study is to highlight the importance of innovation in public administration in achieving social transformation. Analyzing the relationship between the two main ideas of the paper - innovation and sustainable social change - as well as their application in administrative sciences and encouraging creative projects to improve the quality of life of citizens are the objectives of the study.

Adapting public administration to meet the demands and needs of citizens is at the heart of improving public services. The Europe 2020 plan highlights the need for innovation in a smart, sustainable and inclusive society, which calls on national governments and public administrations to address complex social and societal issues. The paper draws on literature research, applications of these ideas in other nations, and the application and evaluation of the data collected. A case study examining how the City of Brasov maintains public services and responds to complex problems underpins the final section of the article. The social and economic effects of the activities carried out by this local public administration in Brasov county on people's lives and the changes brought about within the city are the results of the study. The report highlights the importance of involving researchers and practitioners in bringing about social change and the need for public institutions to adopt a strong and continuous innovative approach. This study exposes excellent practices in local public administration and advances knowledge on the topics.

Change management is a methodical way of approaching change or modification of an organization's objectives, procedures and technology. The primary objective of change management is to execute tactics that facilitate and regulate change while helping individuals adapt to change.

The creation of a new public service for local and regional interest is the result of proactive measures that can be taken by the public administration, requiring the formation of new agreements with other cities or counties or regions or areas of activity.

Fig. 1. Types of services of general interest in Romania, year 2023, [1]

Where new EU legislation leads to the creation of a new service, national legislation must specify the scope, priorities and resources required for the establishment and operation of the service. In order to achieve effective collaboration, it is essential that all parties involved have a common understanding, reach consensus on the necessary steps and synchronize their objectives. The successful implementation of cross-sectoral measures relies on the administration allocating resources and setting priorities in order to achieve pre-established common objectives.

Basic details on procedures in public infrastructure services

Each public authority and organization contributing to the provision of a public service operates in accordance with the laws and regulations of that country. In order to ensure the integrity of Community public services, it is essential to preserve the validity of information and data protection when information is exchanged between two organizations. This applies to both the state providing the information and the state receiving it. This component of interoperability refers to the collaboration of organizations, such as authorities and public administration institutions, from different sectors to achieve mutually agreed objectives. Organizational interoperability includes merging systems, streamlining business processes and sharing relevant data. Organizational interoperability aims to meet the needs of the user community by providing services that are readily available, clearly recognisable, quickly accessible and user-oriented.

To ensure efficient and effective collaboration between different public bodies and organizations and to deliver public services at European level, it is necessary for them to synchronize their existing business processes or even create and implement new ones.

When business processes are aligned, they are documented in a standardised way. This is done to ensure that all relevant authorities and public administration institutions that are involved in the provision of public services are able to understand the overall business processes and their respective responsibilities.

The fundamental tasks of management. Own assessments

In order to deliver a public service effectively, public affairs management needs to document its business procedures and reach agreement on how these procedures should interact with each other.

There needs to be a clearly defined framework for the relationship between service providers and service customers to meet the requirements of service orientation, which serves as the basis for the conceptual model for public services.

To do this, it is necessary to identify tools that can be used to formally establish collaborative efforts, to provide mutual support and to link operational procedures that are linked to service provision. Memoranda of Understanding on collaborative activities and collaboration are examples of such documents. Service level agreements that are approved by the public administration bodies involved are other examples of such instruments.

It is necessary for the public administration to build distinct organizational links to establish an effective public service framework.

In order to maintain the accuracy of data and to guarantee the continuity and reliability of the services provided to public authorities, institutions, individuals and businesses, change management is an essential activity to be carried out. This is because the provision of a public

service requires the concerted efforts of a number of different parties who are involved in the production or use of the components of that service.

Authorities involved in the provision of public services need to reach consensus on change management processes to ensure that these services continue to be provided without disruption.

Organizations are able to interpret and manage information from different sources due to semantic interoperability. Consequently, this ensures that the precise significance of the information is understood and maintained throughout the interactions that take place between individual parties. Services that are of significant interest are defined by the EU White Paper and include both economic and non-economic services that are advantageous to everybody. Integrated services are one component of services required for the general welfare of the people; they meet the needs of both local and zonal (areal) populations.

The municipal and zonal (areal) authorities has the responsibility of offering user-specific, efficient, and effective services. Having the money at their disposal, they have to answer to the voters and the general public for the quality of these services.

To this end, district and municipal governments must assess and evaluate a cost analyzis as a foundation for assessing the effectiveness and caliber of services provided in their jurisdiction. Mechanisms for this assessment must involve benchmarking against certain criteria.

Fig. 2 The fundamental tasks of management. Own assessments

The term "Integrated Service of Local and Zonal (area) Interest" (SIILZ) describes services offered by qualified suppliers who have demonstrated their material and intellectual capacities through contracts and other documentation. Delivery of these services is done in the public interest. According to the legal rules of the service, the SIILZ can be built at the level depicted in Figure 2, which arranges five procedures:

Procedures A is for disaster readiness;

Procedures B is for managing relevant information;

Procedures C is for carrying out unforeseen emergency works;

Procedures D is for managing activities required by specific regulations; and

Procedures E is for environmental monitoring.

Part of the study, representatives of public interest service providers and the general public were polled and informed about the EU White Charter on Services of General Interest. As stressed in the White Paper, services of general interest—a pillar of the European social model—must be made readily available and of excellent quality to all EU citizens and businesses. The White Paper emphasizes the need of guaranteeing that everyone has access to services of common interest in order to maintain the social and territorial coherence and economic competitiveness of Europe.

Building sector-specific data structures that act as building blocks is the first step in the semantic interoperability process. Following their construction, it is very necessary that the organizations that are directly involved reach a consensus on the interpretation of the information that is communicated. Significant challenges are posed by the fact that the linguistic, cultural, legal and administrative environments of Member States are very different from each other.

The following components are included in the semantic interoperability framework that builds on the EIF: In the context of data structures and the relationships between them, semantic interoperability refers to the relevance of data structures. This includes improving the vocabulary used for data transfers and ensuring that all communicating entities have a common knowledge of the data structures.

Defining the structure, layout and patterns of the information to be shared is what is meant by the term 'syntactic interoperability'.

To achieve semantic interoperability at the European level requires, at the very least, compliance with a set of standards and rules.

There is a consensus among groups that are both sectoral and cross-sectoral on the use of semantic interoperability resources at EU level - Established processes and methods for creating semantic interoperability resources.

The technical components involved in the process of integrating information systems are those that are referred to as technical interoperability. There are a number of components that are included in this, including interface standards, connection services, application integration services, data integration services, data presentation and sharing, and so on.

Politically, legally, administratively and to some extent semantically, public administration institutions have various characteristics that differentiate them from each other. On the other hand, technical interoperability is not specific to them. The use of codified specifications is recommended to ensure technological compatibility. Examples of such specifications are the standards defined in Directive 98/34/EC or the specifications developed by ICT industry fora and consortia.

Change management for public service re-engineering

While administrative simplicity of public services and work process re-engineering are the main goals, the report also includes some doable suggestions for modernizing public services from the standpoint of beneficiaries.

Work process re-engineering is the process of completely reevaluating and restructuring work processes inside an organization in order to significantly alter important performance measures like cost, quality, and service delivery speed. Reengineering seeks to bring about significant rather than gradual change and concentrates on ongoing enhancements in participatory service delivery that will benefit all socioeconomic groups equally.

Reducing legal requirements and the need to show eligibility criteria—such as information to be submitted by the applicant and supporting documentation—is known as administrative simplification.

An inventive approach to reconsidering the provision of public services is beneficiary-centeredness, which puts the user experience, creativity, and co-creation ahead of quantitative data and linear models.

The methods of tariff computation are not analyzed in this approach; this work will be done in a different exercise. According to the Society for Human Resource Management (SHRM), change management is defined as the act of accessing and deliberately using information, techniques, and resources to adapt to change. In addition, it encompasses the establishment and implementation of strategies, structures, processes and technologies to have the ability to adapt to changes in external conditions and the environment in which the organization operates.

Assuring the effective execution of new company strategies, products, and processes is the main goal of change management. Reducing the degree of any unanticipated consequences that implementation may have is essential to reaching this objective.

Several difficulties arise in managing organizational change. Several principles must be given priority in order to manage change inside an organization with the greatest potential outcomes. We shall now go into three of these tactics in the paragraphs that follow in order to make the change management process easier for leaders.

Integrity and public candor

Employers who want to guarantee the effective execution of change must be transparent and honest with all information that affects their staff. Because so many workers find change uncomfortable, openness in managing change helps establish trust and rapport with them.

Work to keep communication regular.

To what extent employees are prepared to participate in conversation before, during, and after significant changes inside the company depends significantly on the connections that are built with them. Even in the absence of inquiries, leaders might start conversations with staff members to learn about their viewpoints on the events in their immediate surroundings. Every stakeholder has the chance to voice their opinions, so any misunderstandings may be immediately and easily settled.

Needful information easily accessible

If staff workers cannot easily access entire information and records, then just ownership of them is insufficient. Using a centralized system that houses all necessary paperwork and data streamlines the change management procedure.

Methodologies that are effective in transition management

In business, change is an inevitable reality. The rapid advancement of technology, the ever-changing marketplace and the growing needs of customers require businesses to be able to adapt and discover successful strategies to survive and thrive.

However, even the most well-intentioned efforts to bring about change within an organization can be met with opposition from staff.

Fig. 3 The fundamental scope of management. Own assessments

Managing change in a company is a process that is both strategic and continuous, aiming to successfully implement change within the organization.

Change is something that needs to be carefully thought through and implemented, whether it is implementing new technology, reorganizing an organization or changing its culture.

Successfully managing change and overcoming resistance from employees are therefore two of the most important procedures for a company's success.

Resistance to change: underlying reasons and symptoms of resistance

When employees are faced with change, they frequently show resistance. Employee resistance to change can be attributed to a number of different factors. Fear of the unknown can manifest itself, for example, when someone is faced with the task of responding to new demands and duties.

At other times, resistance to change may be fuelled by concern about losing a job, outdated skills or techniques, lack of trust in leaders or even comfort with the status quo. All of these factors can contribute to resistance to change.

Regardless of the underlying reasons, this resistance can slow down or even halt the implementation of change altogether and have a negative effect on both employee morale and productivity.

Resistance to change can manifest itself in a variety of ways, from outright antagonism or sabotage to lack of collaboration and indifference to change.

Because this is the case, it is essential that leaders and managers have an understanding of these causes and confront opposition in a way that is both successful and sensitive. It is extremely important for leaders to pay attention to these expressions and respond to opposition in a way that is both constructive and productive.

Overcoming resistance to change: coping strategies that work

When trying to overcome resistance to change, it is essential to use a comprehensive strategy that takes into account both the technical and human components of the situation.. Transparent and compassionate communication is the first step.

Business executives must from the outset clearly and openly convey the benefits and reasons for change. This is required to make sure that employees understand the plan and justification for the change as well as the stages and procedures of the process:

a. Value and include the employees in your work

Participating in the planning and decision-making process with employees can help to increase their degree of acceptance and commitment to change. Creating an environment where staff members feel appreciated and involved can help to lower resistance to change and encourage a feeling of ownership over it.

b. Additionally included are training and continuing education.

Giving staff members ongoing chances and resources for training and development can increase their confidence and degree of comfort in handling change. These can help staff members acquire the competencies needed in the setting of the new demands of change.

c. Rewarding and praising others

Acknowledging the efforts and achievements of employees might help to inspire and promote good behavior among them during the transformation process. Offering material incentives or public recognition might help to build support for change.

d. Patterning the desired behavior

Leaders should show by their own deeds and behaviors that they are adaptable and willing to change. Employee perceptions and behavior may be positively impacted by exhibiting a positive attitude and confidence in the process of change.

e. Emotional management and resiliency building

Overcoming opposition requires first controlling employee emotions and attending to their issues. Leaders must be understanding of the emotions and worries of their employees and should also provide support and resources to deal with these problems.

Finally, in a world that is continually changing, the success of a business depends on the intricate procedures of managing change and overcoming employee resistance. Company leaders' reluctance to change may be as much as possible minimized by using a thorough and

all-encompassing approach that emphasizes open communication and engaged employees. Enough resources and support, the example of the desired behavior and culture, and the recognition of accomplishments are all elements that help teams navigate change successfully and can eventually result in innovation and long-term success.

Fig. 4 The interoperability functions in processes. Own assessments

Conclusions

Why do inside our company we oppose change?

I searched the specialist bibliographies to find solutions to this question, and I can give you an overview of the viewpoints that I thought were important.

Although everyone of us has a natural inclination to feel autonomous, everyone is aware that individuals are by nature dependent on one another.

We act to create an environment where we may freely express ourselves because we want to separate ourselves, at some time in our lives, from our families, our schools, or any other form of institution that we believe limits our freedom.

For instance, the desire to ascend to the top of the organizational hierarchy together with the independence to take initiative and make decisions results in the development of the human being into a functioning adult. This grownup is the one that adds the knowledge of their own worth to a set of goals, hobbies, aspirations, or projects.

Therefore, the ability of organizations to respond to basic psychological needs of humans as well as to contain and realize the individual goals of its members (in a more comprehensive, efficient, and expedient way) may explain the reason for their formation and existence.

Change management is therefore one of the biggest challenges of our day and is starting to worry businesses and other organizations constantly.

One specific component of this issue in Romania transcends the conventional approaches of addressing opposition to change. This is owing to the mindset of our people. It's called overconfidence or overestimating one's own skills in relation to those of others ("I am more capable / more prepared, more..., than others").

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